

ISic0616

A Roman honours his mother

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material**Object**

block

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Autopsy

2018.07.17 Prag

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Agrigentum

Place of origin (modern)

Agrigento

Provenance

Found in 1925 in material to the east of the 'Oratory of Phalaris' (Marconi writes "ritrovata tra le macerie a oriente del tempietto")

Coordinates

37.296666, 13.588604

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Agrigento, Museo Regionale Archeologico Pietro Griffo, inventory S.2319

Physical Description

A large rectangular block of shell-bearing limestone, intact on top, left, right and behind, but damaged below. Appears intact lower right underside, so the only significant loss/damage is the lower left corner. The left edge of the stone is clearly preserved, which implies at least one additional block originally stood to the left.

Dimensions

Height 36.5 cm

Width 139.5 cm

Depth 20.5 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: 90-105 mm

Line 2: 85-95 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: 30-45 mm

Text

1. [---]us · M(arci) · f(ilius) · Ter(etina tribu) · (vac.undefi)Pius

2. [---]f(iliam) · matrem · suam ·

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

[devo]TE, De Miro 2000; the first letter preserves part of an upper horizontal, the second is either an E or an F

Translation (en)

[---]us Pius, son of Marcus, of the tribe Teretina

Translation (it)

[---]us Pius figlio di Marco della tribù Teretina [---] sua madre

Commentary

The surviving traces at the start of line two are most readily compatible in the context with TF, which would be T(iberi) f(iliam)

as the filiation of the honoured mother's name. The suggestion of De Miro to read *devote*

is less plausible. De Miro's suggestion to read *ter pius*

as 'thrice pius' rather than tribal and cognomen/epithet cannot be followed.

The first part of the text continued on another block to the left. The interpunct after 'suam' in line 2 and the edge of the stone suggest this is the right hand end of the text. The layout could imply another line below on another block, perhaps containing the explanation for the honours. It has been generally assumed that the stone belongs to the so-called 'Oratory of Phalaris', which in turn was suggested by the excavator Marconi (1926) to be a heroon. The idea that it was a tomb or heroon, rather than a temple was firmly rejected by Wilson (1990: 31 and 356 n.102). Campagna (2007) has however rightly questioned whether there is in fact any evidence for the association. The block is the same stone as the temple; it does however show no traces of the stucco which covers much of the exterior of the temple. The formulation of nominative individual and then accusative for the mother makes it more likely that this is an honorific (perhaps a statue base?) rather than a funerary inscription, albeit using the Greek accusative for the honorand (Latin would ordinarily use a dative) - this latter feature could either imply a Roman / Italian immigrant to the island or else a 'romanised' Sicilian. Honours of this sort for a woman in Latin epigraphy at this date are rare.

Digital identifiers:

TM 491463

EDR 129884

EDCS 26201044

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0616. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4338095>

Photo J. Prag, courtesy Museo Regionale Archeologico Pietro Griffo